

EFFECTS OF PRINCIPALS' SUPERVISORY TECHNIQUES ON WORK PERFORMANCE OF NEWLY HIRED TEACHERS

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Effects of Principals' Supervisory Techniques on Work Performance of Newly Hired Teachers

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Abstract

This research aims to assess the effects of supervisory techniques of the principals on newly hired teachers' work performance in Marilao North District in Division of Bulacan. The study may contribute to the upskilling and retooling of the implemented supervisory techniques to assist the newly hired teachers to adopt and respond to the emerging circumstances brought by the pandemic. The theoretical framework of the study focused on the contingency theory of leadership in line with situational aspect and used CIPP as the conceptual framework to diversify the process and produce quality outcome and implications. The respondents of the study were the 117 newly hired teachers and 9 principals identified through purposive random sampling technique. The data responses were gathered through online questionnaire and triangulate it through FGD to deepen the result. Mixed method was used to determine the effects of the variables. Descriptive correlation and regression analysis was used to interpret and analyze the data which presents the strengths and significant effects and its impact. The findings of the study claimed that the supervisory techniques of the principals have a descriptive interpretation of "Very High" while the work performance of newly hired teachers obtained a "High" descriptive interpretation based on the correlated and regression analysis. The study also revealed that the level of principals' supervisory techniques towards the work performance of the newly hired teachers is correlated to the teaching experiences to varying extent but not significant. The findings revealed that there is no significant effects between the principals' supervisory techniques and work performance of the newly hired teachers. Thus, principals may continuously supervise and scaffold all newly hired teachers to improve their work performance for the attainment of the department's vision and mission.

Keywords: *supervisory techniques, newly hired teachers, work performance*

Introduction

Philippine education speaks of a system whereby an individual or a group of people in a given place and time is influenced, molded, and modified for the upliftment of life towards global competitiveness. The changes of various national and global frameworks in education and the changing characteristics of the 21st century learners necessitate a call for the rethinking of the professional standards and techniques for the school heads and supervisors in providing educational supervision. In the dynamic landscape of education, the success of teachers plays a pivotal role in shaping the learning experiences of students. As they embark on their teaching careers, these educators face a myriad of challenges, ranging from classroom management to curriculum implementation. Amidst these challenges, the role of supervisory techniques employed by school administrators, particularly principals, emerges as a crucial factor influencing the work performance and professional growth of the teachers. To come up with a long term evidenced-based mechanism, the study aimed to formulate the effects of supervisory techniques for the continuous enhancement and development of teachers' work performance towards effective supervision pertaining to instructional and educational supervision, provision of technical assistance and quality assurance for new initiative or curriculum of Department of Education.

In the Governance of Basic Education in the Philippines (Republic Act 9155 s. 2001), the school head has the responsibility to encourage and enhance staff development. This role is very vital in supervising and assisting the newly hired teachers since he/she is the person most accountable for the teachers' welfare. Thus, there is a need to recognize that the first two or three years of teaching is critical in developing teachers' capabilities and that newly hired teachers should not be left alone to sink or swim in their profession (Clement, 2021).

Quality learning outcomes are produced by quality teachers, who are supported by effective school leaders. As indicated in DepEd Order No.87 s. 2010, School-based Mentoring Program (SBMP) was institutionalized among all elementary and secondary schools to mobilize competent mentors to work out teachers' work performance. This also paved the way as part of the DepEd Order No. 43, s. 2017, Teacher Induction Program (TIP) wherein newly hired teachers are well-taken care of during their first year in teaching by way of contributing to them the sense of well-being and professional development. As agreed by Bilbao et al. (2018), TIP through supervisory techniques has contributed positively to enhancing the teachers' knowledge, skills, values, and commitment to the profession.

Additionally, the DepEd improve the program as Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT) which is a systematic and comprehensive professional development program for beginning teachers with 0 to 3 years of teaching experience that has been developed to improve their knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values (KSAVs), and increase their confidence in teaching to make them effective and efficient teachers who nurture the potentials, abilities, and talents of every learner. A good induction program addresses the important issues of transition from being a preservice teacher to being a teacher and sets the tone for a teacher's personal and professional identity (Ryan, 2020).

According to Osakwe (2020), supervision is concerned with the provision of professional assistance and guidance to teachers and even to the learners who are geared towards the achievement of effective teaching and learning in the school. In line with this, principal provides a professional guidance to teachers in order to improve their competencies for effective teaching process to enhance the learning and growth of the students. Meaning, through the principal supervision it may provide meaningful feedback and direction to teachers that can have profound effect in the learning that occurs in their work performance.

The newly adopted standards, which are consistent with the MATATAG reforms, set out clear expectations of school principals at different career stages, from beginning to exemplary practice. The standards encourage greater proficiency, provide support for professional learning and development, help identify development needs, and facilitate uniform assessment of work performance. In line with this, DepEd implemented a Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) which covers the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) wherein it was a shared undertaking between the superior and the employee that allows an open discussion of work expectations, Key Results Areas (KRAs), Objectives and how these align to overall departmental goals that provides a venue for agreement on standards of performance and behaviors which lead to professional and personal growth in the organization.

Moreover, the extent to which teachers achieve their important role of imparting knowledge is contingent on their effective work performance which explained by Lopez (2021) that effective teaching, which consists of the mastery of the subject matter, instructional tools, class management and adequacy of supervision produces better instructional performance.

In the same manner, Ekpoh and Eze (2020) stated that the teachers' work performance involves all the activities carried out by the teacher to achieve the desired effects on students. It involves teachers' participation in the overall running of the school in order to achieve the expected objective and goals of the school. The school then performs in an unusually successful work environment which has school manager who does his/her task in an exceptional manner.

According to Chidi and Victor (2020), teachers' work performance refers to the extent to which teachers are committed to pedagogical delivery and display of moral uprightness and academic excellence in the teaching profession. It is concerned with overall ability of the teachers to exhibit the right attitude to work, be committed and dedicated to the teaching roles and making deliberate efforts toward the attainment of educational goals and objectives.

On the other hand, Glickman (2020) explained that the technical skills enable the principal to have that ability to use the knowledge, methods, and techniques of instructional supervision so as to support the teacher in the instructional activities which helps to improve teacher performance. The principal may not have all the technical skills but should at least possess overall knowledge of the function of supervisors, that is knowing how to prepare scheme of work, preparing of lesson plan, induction of new teachers and possessing of clinical supervision knowledge is also important for effective supervision. In relatable manner, principals tend to workshop and facilitate the progress of teacher's performance based on the submitted output, lesson log and other accomplishment reports handed down to them, wherein they can input feedback and recommendations to develop teachers' work performance.

Equally, Aliyu and Umaru (2018) found out that the principals should intensify more effort in their instructional supervision in term of inspecting student notebooks to ascertain the level of coverage of topics and supporting teachers in their lesson, in terms of scheme of work, lesson plan and lesson note this will help to improve teachers' performance. Thus, the importance of supervisory techniques may help in achieving teachers' better performance and this can be accelerated through supervision practices like visiting classrooms, appraising, and workshops/seminars (Obi, 2019). However, in this time of pandemic, principal may not execute those practices because of the changed learning modality in school hence they continuously find outlet to monitor the learning delivery of the teachers. Likewise, the principals conducted an online class supervision, created online group pages for monitoring, weekly conduct of video conferencing and establishing of different training sessions or learning action cell to make a bridging in the gap during the new normal setting of education.

Based on Igwe (2021), class observation is also part of the supervisory techniques by which the educational leader is aiding the teacher to improve both instructional techniques and the students' learning process. This idea elaborated that the main purpose of the principals' class observation is for the improvement of the teaching and learning process in the school. However, it was noted that some of the teachers are always fearful and scared of supervision and do not take it in a positive outlook. Furthermore, in new normal education, they may see that class observation will no longer applicable since there is no face-to-face but the educators like the principal did not stop facilitating the class observation thus, they created different venture to continuously guide and monitor the teachers specifically in online class and even in working out the developed video lessons of the teachers.

Additionally, the establishment of continuously supervision will then strengthen teachers' content knowledge and pedagogy, maintained the learning environment, kept the diversity of the learners, maintained students' interest, established a well-planned and designed curriculum, organized an assessment and evaluation for the progress of learners and demonstrated various related activities to contribute to teaching and learning process.

Conclusively, these practices had deeply held notions about the work performance of the teachers in relation with the supervisory techniques of principals that are varied alternative modes of processes of schools under the scope of their responsibility during this changing system of education. This study may contribute to the upskilling and retooling of the implemented supervisory techniques to

assist the newly hired teachers to adapt and respond more quickly and effectively to the emerging circumstances associated with the challenges brought by the emerging curriculum.

Because of the abovementioned issues and conflicts existing between and among research findings, the objective of the study was to assess the impact of principals' supervisory techniques on work performance of newly hired teachers in public elementary schools in one of the districts in Bulacan that may formulate holistic implication, projects, and interventions in the conduct of effective supervisory enhancement plan for the implementation of the new curriculum applied and delivered by the newly hired teachers in schools, based on the results of the study.

Research Questions

The major problem of the study was to assess the effects of principals' supervisory techniques on work performance of newly hired teachers in public elementary schools of Marilao North District in Division of Bulacan. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent is the level of principals' supervisory techniques in public elementary schools be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. instructional supervision;
 - 1.2. monitoring of work scheme;
 - 1.3. class observation technique;
 - 1.4. inspection of learning materials and teaching resources; and
 - 1.5. workshop and demonstration techniques?
2. What is the level of work performance of newly hired teachers in public elementary schools of Marilao North District in Bulacan in terms of:
 - 2.1. content knowledge and pedagogy;
 - 2.2. learning environment and diversity of learners;
 - 2.3. curriculum and planning & assessment and reporting;
 - 2.4. personal growth and professional development & personal growth and professional development; and
 - 2.5. plus factor?
3. Does the level of principals' supervisory techniques significantly affect the work performance of newly hired teachers in terms of the following years of teaching experience/s:
 - 3.1. 1 to 2 years;
 - 3.2. 2 to 3 years; and
 - 3.3. 3 years but less than 4 years?
4. Is there significant impact between the principals' supervisory techniques to the work performance of newly hired teachers?
5. What implications may be drawn from the findings of the study for the improvement of the implementation of the principals' supervisory techniques on work performance of newly hired teachers as a basis for the conduct of supervisory enhancement plan?

Literature Review

Supervisory Techniques

On the study conducted by Ekpoh and Eze (2020), revealed the obtained results that there is a significant relationship exist between principals' supervisory techniques in terms of classroom visitation, workshop techniques and teachers' work performance. Based on the findings, teachers' work performances would be enhanced when they are properly supervised by the principals using the various supervisory techniques.

As Bago (2018) emphasized, the roles of school heads focus on the different dimensions like in curriculum implementation, utilization of learning resource center and materials, preparation of reports and financial statements, conduct of research, participation in training and seminars, and in carrying out health and safety practices, including classroom management. Thus, instructional supervisors are expected to provide technical support on the above-mentioned dimensions to improve access and delivery of quality basic education.

The stated claim of these studies served as a guide in paving out the effects of monitoring of work scheme, workshop, and demonstration techniques as part of the supervisory techniques applied by the principal in the current study.

Ambrose (2020) also claimed that the principal and educational agencies are significantly affecting both the interest of the teachers and students on effective teaching and learning of school subjects by using appropriate supervisory measures in motivating and arousing them. It also added the idea that this would enhance teachers' productivity and work performance on the requisite skills. Additionally, the regular supervision on the performance of the teacher has a very significant positive effect in their teaching process, which means that the more effective and regular supervision of supervisors can highly develop the work performance of the teachers. (Abdullah et al., 2020)

In this manner, Patolot (2019) highly emphasized on assistance for newly hired teachers with teaching rather than assessing them in

these formative years of teaching, in which mentoring appears to be a preferred support mechanism as it draws upon the expertise of existing school staff who can provide immediate benefits to the beginning teacher. However, increasing benefits to newly hired teachers that include mentoring for effective teaching require quality preparation and careful selection of mentors. This implies for principal who can effectively supervise the newly hired teachers through their most difficult years of teaching. Wherein the present study used this claim as a basis through quality supervisory techniques for newly hired teachers that may develop a repertoire of problem-solving strategies for dealing with the practicalities and complexities associated with contextual school and current teaching situations.

Lictao (2021) in his study pointed out that competent supervision and administration do not only aid persons to solve their problems but also provide conditions under which all may participate as free agent in the solution of common problems. The 32 principals must pave the way for the best by managing the school efficiently and by providing the most favorable condition for the exercise and use of teachers' initiative, resourcefulness, and ingenuity. Generally, the basic functions of supervision are managing and improving the teaching learning situation. School principal must be conversant with modern supervision and learn to work with the public to lead their staff in instructional improvement through effective supervisory practices and efficient school management.

Abovementioned study may contribute as guide in this present study in paving out the importance of effective supervision towards the development of the work performances of the teachers.

According to Sindhvad (2019), the factors that promote principals' sense of self-efficacy and outcome expectancy for providing teacher incentives that motivate improved curriculum instruction is key to the formulation of school-based management policies and development of interventions supporting the school principal in this new role and organizational environment. Similarly, Azainil et al. (2019) highlighted the indicators of the study which explains that there is an influence between the principal's supervision competence and school culture on teacher performance. In other words, the higher the supervisory competence of the school principal, the better the outcome will be performed by the teacher.

Furthermore, Alonge and Oyewole (2018) explained the data gathered and analyzed in the study conducted indicates that there is a significant relationship between instructional supervisory role performance of principals and the motivation of their teachers. Likewise, this significantly positive relationship was found between experience of principals in performing their instructional supervisory roles and the motivation of their teachers. Moreover, the principals can influence in both the supervisory and instructional domains which explains that it is strongly related to the teachers' active participation in decision making, suggesting the benefits of mutuality in school leadership. (Marks & Nance, 2019)

Work Performance

The work performance of teachers had been enhanced in the teaching-learning process by investing and allocating an adequate amount for the professional development program. In more specific idea, teachers should not be confined only in the four walls of the classroom, instead allowed them to keep abreast in all the updates in teaching that asserts personal and professional development. Teachers are duty bound to work with other people in the community aside from doing daily routines in education. Thus, training and workshops whether in local, national, or international that promote the better performance of teachers in teaching and in fostering activities that attract the people in the community to participate for the betterment of the school are necessary. (Baluyos & Rivera, 2019)

According to Mary (2020), teacher's performance has contingent upon intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, if there is management of good personnel, good infrastructure, and culture climate, teaching materials, and good supervision. Authors have been described motivation as intrinsic and extrinsic in nature and both extrinsic and intrinsic motivation affects teacher's performance if the intervening effects are available. Particularly, the teachers' work performance can be measured by supervision of school activities, regular and early reporting at school, adequate teaching preparation, general punctuality among others and participating in extra-curricular activities. Likewise, the teachers' satisfaction from job and performance leads to their retention in teaching field and schools as well. This study may serve as guide to the researcher to seek the different factors affecting the work performance of newly hired teachers.

Additionally, Ermita (2017) explained that the performance of teachers and the implementation of supervision in the category by the principal has a positive effect on the performance of teachers. This means that the better implementation of the supervision by the higher school principal or increasing the performance of teachers in performing their duties. In other words, the effective principal instructional supervisory practices are critical and veritable tools to propel teachers for better work performance which in turn influence students' achievement. (Sunday et al., 2019)

Conversely, as stated by Yusuf (2020) poor work performance can be influenced by the leadership quality that does not indicate teacher's performance identification. In addition, the active personality of employees by strengthening the influence of leadership in identifying work performance monitoring problems regarding what they do. Along with this idea the teacher's convenience is directly related to commitment, behavior as an executor at work, employee turnover, absence, dedication, and performance. The level of work is important to attract and retain talented teachers, therefore good supervision may impart to ensure a competitive advantage in the work.

The former studies were parallel to the present study, since the researcher included the instructional supervision as part of the supervisory techniques of the principals relating to the work performance, this may serve as a support to the objective the study.

Moreover, Donaldson and Mavrogordato (2018) stated that school leaders' framing of teacher performance and their efforts to improve instruction reveal the cognitive, relational, and organizational aspects of working with low-performing teachers and, if necessary, pursuing removal. Notably, this study found that cognitive and relational factors were important in school leaders' teacher improvement efforts. In the same way, the implementation by peer teachers yielded statistically positive results on both collaboration and commitment to teaching scales. It explained that commitment is highly related to the teacher's work performance which deeply contribute to the overall productivity of students and school. However, there is a weaker effect produced for commitment to school, trust in administration, and outcome expectations scales. In contrast, implementation by principals yielded statistically positive effects for all dependent measures. (Mart, 2018)

Methodology

Research Design

The method of research used in the study was a descriptive-correlational method which is utilized to determine the effects of supervisory techniques on work performance. Correlational research is a type of research method, in which a researcher measures two variables, understands and assesses the statistical relationship between them with no influence from any extraneous variable. More so, document analysis was also done to gather the work performance of the teacher-respondents.

A mixed-methods design was used in the study to determine the effects of supervisory techniques on work performance. It is characterized by the combination of at least one qualitative and one quantitative research component. This method is utilized by the researcher for answering the research question/s with validity nevertheless have various reasons or purposes for strengthening the research study and its conclusions. It focuses on collecting, analyzing, and mixing both quantitative and qualitative data in the study. Its central premise is the use of quantitative and qualitative approaches that provides a better understanding of research problems than either approach alone. (Creswell & Clark, 2017). Through the use of mixed methods, the researcher has a choice to perform data analysis. The researcher could analyze interview data and questionnaire data of one inquiry independently. It is also possible to let the interview questions depend upon the outcomes of the analysis of the questionnaire data or vice versa, in that case the research activities are performed dependently. Similarly, the empirical effect and process in this study with the purpose of expansion might be investigated or the processed study might take the effect and outcome as given result.

Respondents

Since the study was conducted in Marilao North District, the respondents of the study were sampled from this population. The respondents of the study were the one hundred seventeen (117) newly hired teachers with 1 to more than 3 years but less than 4 years in service in public elementary schools of Marilao North District in Bulacan.

All the principals of the nine schools were invited to participate in the research to address and provide information on the research questions more sufficiently.

Instrument

The study utilized a structured instrument that assess the supervisory techniques of the principals and the work performance of newly hired teachers. The instrument was adopted from the study conducted by Umoh (2013) entitled "Supervisory Role of Principals in Enhancing Teachers' Professional Development in Secondary Schools in Kitui West District, Kenya" which was published in The Catholic University of Eastern Africa and available online thru CUAE Bitstream.

In the same manner, it was designed to measure the utilization of the principals' supervisory techniques in terms of instructional supervision, monitoring of work scheme, class observation technique, inspection of learning materials and teaching resources, and workshop and demonstration techniques, the adopted instrument were devised by the researcher into 25-item survey questionnaires from the objectives and performance indicators of the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF) of the principal which was adjusted and modified based on the requirements of the curriculum in education wherein it was developed for criteria-based reliability analysis.

Procedure

The questionnaire method was the mode of data gathering. Each of the respondents was given a well- structured, well-instructed, and standardized set of questions to assess the effects of principals' supervisory on their work performance.

In gathering the abovementioned data, the researcher will carry out the following procedure:

Pre-Implementation Phase:

After the research proposal and upon approval of the Research Ethics Committee, the researcher will write a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of Bulacan and the data privacy associate of the school to ask permission to gather specific data and conduct a survey on the school's behalf.

Upon approval, as proof of compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 the researcher will be able to signed legal documents (i.e.,

Memorandum of Agreement, Terms of Data Usage).

Actual Implementation Phase:

A letter will send to the Schools Division Superintendent of Bulacan to ask permission to conduct the study. With the approval, the researcher will distribute the informed consent form and developed online survey forms to the respondents.

With the informed consent of the respondents, the researcher may conduct a recorded online FGD via Google Meet as the platform of communication that will be scheduled at the most convenient time of the respondents.

To observe health and safety protocols, the researcher may a facemask while maintaining social distancing in delivering the consent and other letter to the respondents.

Post-Implementation Phase:

The responses will be collected from the respondents. Retrieval of data was through online data gathering (google forms) and/or remote printed survey.

The researcher may check if all the items are answered religiously for the conduct of the study.

After securing the data, the responses shall be made ready for data analyzing process, tabulation, and statistical treatment.

Ethical Considerations

The Graduate Studies Department of La Consolacion University Philippines (LCUP) has recently introduced the determination and implementation of specific ethical considerations in any thesis and dissertation to ensure that ethical requirements are complied with to safeguard research participants' interests.

Before gathering the data, the research study should undergo Research Ethics Review, thus the researcher should submit the following:

Endorsement from the Dean/Vice President for Graduate Studies that the research study was already defended and that has complied with the recommendations of the panel.

Cover letter addressed to the LCUP Research Ethics Committee.

A copy of the research manuscript / research protocol / investigator's brochure and other pertinent documents related to the review of your study protocol.

Hence, the researcher secured institutional clearances and permission from both LCUP's Graduate Studies Department and in the Schools District Office of Marilao North in Division of Bulacan.

The following ethical considerations were put into place for this research undertaking:

The researcher obtained the Schools Division Superintendent's permission on the survey to navigate their records at the said institution more conveniently. They were also informed that their names and other valuable information would not appear in the final thesis.

The dignity and wellbeing of the principals and teachers were protected. They would not be harmed in any form or placed in an uncomfortable position.

The researcher will provide inform consent from the necessary persons that includes essential information stated in the preceding portions of the paper. They were also informed that participating in the study was voluntary, ensuring no coercion or deception in participation. Upon agreement, respondents signed an Informed Consent Form with and observance of all ethical principles.

The researchers would treat any information that might be shared in the study with utmost anonymity and confidentiality. No individual identities were used in any reports or publications resulting from the study.

The researcher complied with the declaration of "No Conflict of Interest" stated that the authors whose names were listed certify that they have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent-licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this research.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the outcome of the qualitative analysis of the research questions answers. The results are presented based on the emergent themes, sub-themes, core ideas, and categorization.

Level of Principals' Supervisory Techniques

Principal's supervisory techniques are methods that are used to achieve specific goals, both related to the resolution of teacher problems

in teaching, the problem of principals in developing institutions, and problems related to the quality of education. It also refers to the execution of the improvement of the total teaching-learning situation and condition of the school. As emphasized in the previous related study of Bago (2008), the roles of school principals focus on the different dimensions like in curriculum implementation, utilization of learning resource center and materials, preparation of reports and financial statements, the conduct of research, participation in training and seminars, and in carrying out health and safety practices. In other words, the level of supervisory techniques of the principals was analyzed based on the instructional supervision, monitoring of work scheme, class observation technique, inspection of learning materials and teaching resources, and workshop and demonstration techniques.

Table 1. Mean Scores and Descriptive Equivalent of Level of Principals' Supervisory Techniques in Public Elementary Schools in Marilao North District

<i>Supervisory Techniques</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Instructional Supervision	4.56	0.62	Always Observed
Monitoring of Work Scheme	4.61	0.61	Always Observed
Class Observation Technique	4.60	0.67	Always Observed
Inspection of Learning Materials and Teaching Resources	4.51	0.71	Always Observed
Workshop and Demonstration Techniques	4.64	0.60	Always Observed

The level of supervisory techniques of the public school principals in terms of the characterized variables are presented in Table 5, wherein the Instructional Supervision obtained the mean of 4.56, 4.61 is the accumulated mean of Monitoring of Work Scheme, for the Class Observation Technique attain 4.60 as the mean result, 4.51 in the Inspection of Learning Materials and Teaching Resources, and the Workshop and Demonstration Techniques has the mean of 4.64, and the characterized variables based on the level of principals' supervisory techniques has its equivalent description of "Always Observed".

Based on the computed mean, the Workshop and Demonstration Techniques obtained the highest level of supervisory techniques observed in the principal while the least observed supervisory techniques of the principal are the Inspection of Learning Materials and Teaching Resources.

Additionally, the table indicates that sub-variables on school principals' supervisory techniques were rated by the newly hired teacher – respondents within the weighted mean of 4.50 – 4.65 described as always observed. The teachers gave the highest assessment of school principals' supervisory techniques on Workshop and Demonstration Techniques. The teachers perceived that this is the most observed supervisory technique that their school principals carried out. They were convinced that their school principals did this supervisory technique because it can serve as a basis in their efforts to improve class instruction. Similarly, they described to a great extent the level of principals' supervisory techniques were monitoring of work scheme with 4.61 as mean score and 4.60 to the class observation technique.

This suggests that teachers perceived that their school principals have a great monitoring process and gave suggestions for improvement during the post-conference in their class observation. In the same manner, teachers perceived those school principals to always observe carried out their supervisory techniques in instructional supervision and inspection of learning materials and teaching resources. Teachers were convinced that school principals were serious in the exercise of their supervision and evaluation specifically in inspecting learning materials and teaching resources.

In this insight, the combined survey questionnaires on the supervisory techniques and an online FGD of newly hired teachers elaborated the idea on the level of the principals' supervisory techniques were balanced out. Since the FGD provides chunked information based on their experiences, they summaries the same idea from the survey questionnaires that most of the principal provides new opportunities for their personal and professional growth and implement strategies that can retool their instructional practices, and they proved that inspection of learning materials and teaching resources were also the least practices of their principals because most of the time, the principal will assigned those checking of materials to the Master Teachers or to the Head Teachers. On the other side, the results in the survey questionnaires obtained a high mean score in the class observation techniques of the principals, hence in the FGD, the researcher found out that there were minimal times that the principal observed the newly hired teachers during face-to-face or even virtually because the task of observing the proficient teachers are assigned to the Master Teachers.

In a reasonable statement, the school principals did this function because they were convinced that it could help many teachers in their teaching and work performances. This suggests that the newly hired teachers perceived that their school principals were religious in their responsibilities of supervising and evaluating teachers' pedagogical tasks in the classroom. School principals believed as perceived by their teachers that discharging their supervisory techniques can enhance the teaching and learning process of learners, thus, improve teachers' performance. This finding is consistent with the previous study which indicated that the level of supervisory techniques of the school principals as perceived by their teachers was to a great extent. (Barredo, 2019)

Similarly, Agunwa and Owan (2019) explained that the principals' supervisory, leadership and communication competencies are significantly related to teachers' work performance in terms of instructional delivery, attendance to classes, notes writing, and record-keeping respectively. In other words, both internal and external supervision have a significant influence on the effectiveness of teachers

and has a greater effect on their work performance.

Level of Work Performance of Newly Hired Teachers

A teacher's work performance is defined by Obilade (2002) as duties performed by a teacher at a particular period in their field in achieving organizational goals. Likewise, the work performance can be measured by its ability to: (1) Skills planning: a) assess and set priorities from the field results, b) realistic designing long and short-term plans, c) anticipate the problems that might be and constraints barriers towards achieving the required results; (2) Organizational skills: a). classifying activities for the optimal use of the sources of personnel in order to achieve objectives, b). clearly define responsibilities and limits of authority for subordinates, c) minimize confusion and inefficiency in work operations; (3) Skills directs: a) the ability to guide and supervise b) emphasizes the process of motivation, communication, and leadership; (4) Skill controls: a) Setting a proper procedure for informed on the progress of the work of subordinates, b) identify deviations in the progress of work purposes, c) adapt the job to be able to ensure that the goals set have been achieved. (Dessler, 2017)

Furthermore, the newly hired teachers' work performance was assessed through the rating of their IPCRF, wherein it is an assessment tool for government employees' use that will rate tasks accomplished for a year. It is composed of Key Result Areas (KRAs) which dwells on Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, and Plus Factor with the Performance evaluators as to the quality, efficiency, and timeliness. In order to determine the score obtained, there are performance indicators that show how the objective was performed with ratings: 5- Outstanding, 4-Very Satisfactory, 3-Satisfactory, 2-Unsatisfactory, and 1-Poor Performance.

Table 2. Mean Scores and Descriptive Equivalent of Level of Work Performance of Newly Hired Teachers in Public Elementary Schools in Marilao North District

<i>Key Results Area</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	4.31	0.36	Very Satisfactory
Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	4.28	0.34	Very Satisfactory
Curriculum and Planning	4.24	0.32	Very Satisfactory
Assessment and Reporting	4.30	0.36	Very Satisfactory
Plus Factor	4.14	0.68	Very Satisfactory

The newly hired teachers' work performance was determined by computing its weighted mean with the corresponding description. Table 6 presents the analyzed mean value of the key results area (KRAs) of IPCRF of the teachers, whereas the Content Knowledge and Pedagogy attained the mean score of 4.31, the Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners has the obtaining mean of 4.28, 4.24 is the mean score of Curriculum and Planning, the Assessment and Reporting has gained 4.30 and for the Plus Factor yielded the mean score of 4.14, wherein all the KRAs has its descriptive equivalent of Very Satisfactory (VS).

The table above implies that Content Knowledge and Pedagogy is the highest mean pointer while Plus Factor is the least pointer of the mean score, meaning the newly hired teachers are more performing in terms of applied knowledge of lesson content within and across curriculum teaching areas, they were also evaluated that they used a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner's achievement in literacy and numeracy skills, and the teacher has applied a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.

Hence, the newly hired teachers were also engaged in the aspect of Plus Factors but not as much as the other key results area, which means that the teachers need to extend and performed various related works and activities that may contribute to the teaching-learning process.

In coordination with the FGD results, the feedbacks from the principals were raised during the interview which helps the newly hired teachers to improve their IPCRF because the need evidence to complete the evaluation of their performance were mostly given during their class observation which explained that the quality of feedbacks from the principals were very helpful to further develop their teaching skills.

However, the result of the analyzed IPCRF in the indicator of Plus Factor contradicts to the answers from the interview because most of the responses of the interviewed teachers they stated that they were given more tasks and loads that may represents as the subject coordinator, advisership, and even as a coaching aspect during the school year. Furthermore, most of them stated that they have completed different trainings and webinars as part of Plus Factors wherein in the analyzed result it gained the least among the indicators of KRAs. Additionally, the teachers to a great extent are efficacious in the use of teaching strategies, assessment, and reporting the status of the learners, and producing a conducive learning environment.

They were equipped with knowledge and skills on the different teaching strategies and developing and localizing the curriculum. In other words, teachers can easily facilitate learning to their students by curriculum planning and development.

These structures of the idea were given in the table because the weighted mean of the other KRAs ranges from 4.24 – 4.30 which are

very satisfactory in their performance evaluation. The findings are consistent with the previous study which indicated that the teaching efficacy of teachers in terms of student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management is manifested to a great extent. (Reyes, 2005).

In the same perspective with the study conducted by Sabio and Manalo (2018) revealed that the public elementary school teachers generally yielded a “Very Satisfactory” rating in CBPAST and IPCR during the five years. Since the two instruments (i.e., CBPAST and IPCR) are both self-assessment tools, it is recommended that a more subjective performance assessment tool be utilized like those that involve the participation of the students and the immediate superior of the concerned public school teachers. Additionally, the evaluation procedures and associated instruments provide the framework for assessing teacher performance as it relates to the work performance criteria. Through the objective and unbiased application of this process, work performance strengths and areas for improvement will be identified. This data will be constructively communicated to the teachers and through interaction, a professional growth plan will be developed to support and enhance professional development (Watkins, 2007)

Newly Hired Teachers Years of Teaching Service in Public School

Teaching experience is positively associated with personal and professional achievements gain throughout a teacher’s career. The years of teaching service of the teachers comprises the depth idea about newly hired teachers, wherein gains in teacher effectiveness associated with experience are steepest in teachers’ initial years but continue to be significant as teachers reach the second, and often third, decades of their profession.

Table 3. *Frequencies of Years of Teaching Service in Public School*

<i>Years</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1 – 2 years	13	11.11%
2 – 3 years	57	48.72%
More than 3 but less than 4 years	47	40.17%
Total	117	100.00%

Table 3 further discloses that out of the 117 teachers who filled up their profile on the length of service, 13 or 11.11% have 1 – 2 years in service, 57 or 48.72% have 2 – 3 years, 47 or 40.17% have more than 3 years but less than 4 years in teaching services. It can be construed that the majority (2 – 3 years, and more than 3 but less than 4 years teaching experience) of the teachers in the public elementary school in Marilao North District have been in the service for a quite number of years and a good number of them are new in the service (1 – 2 years).

Significant Effects of Supervisory Techniques to Work Performance in terms of Teaching Experience/s

Newly hired teachers during the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions show varied manifestations of what they experienced as a neophyte in the profession, how they cope up with the diverse challenges they encountered in just a short period of time, to ensure effective teaching-learning, and what insights they could share to other teachers. Through the efforts of their principals to ensure effective teaching-learning, they provide different supervisory techniques to generate the act of diligence, ingenuity, and resourcefulness; openness and respect; support system; and out of the box professional training and developmental plan for the betterment of the work performance of the newly hired teachers.

Moreover, the teaching experiences bring the teachers exposure to various teaching styles, strategies, and classroom management procedures that can breathe new life into a faculty.

These experiences may advance collegiality, collaboration, and instructional improvement. Peer observation fosters personal reflection, imitation or avoidance, and enhanced cooperation between teachers.

Due to the varied nature of this study, naturally, there were some confounding factors that supervisory techniques of the principals may not significantly affect the work performance of the teachers based on teaching experiences since the data were analyzed.

Table 4. *Significant Effects of Supervisory Techniques to Work Performance in terms of Teaching Experience/s*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>r²</i>	<i>p – value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
<i>Supervisory Techniques and Work Performance</i>			
1 to 2 years	0.012	0.721	Not Significant
2 to 3 years	0.013	0.405	Not Significant
More than 3 years but less than 4 years	0.000	0.927	Not Significant

Table 4 presents the results of the correlation analysis that revealed that the level of principals’ supervisory techniques towards the work performance of the newly hired teachers is correlated to the teaching experiences to varying extent. The nature of the relationship is positive which means that in general the higher the level of teaching experiences, the greater effects of supervisory techniques on the work performances of teachers. A closer look at the table, teachers with 1 to 2 years with 0.721, the p-value of 2 to 3 years is 0.405 and 0.927 for more than 3 years but less than 4 years of teaching experiences that have coefficients with associated probability, wherein

they are correlated but not significantly affecting the variables.

Likewise, the factors affecting teachers' performance were investigated. The study covered is considered as a support claim for developing the level of supervisory techniques of the principals in the work performance of teachers with 0-3 years of teaching experience. The results obtained for the findings are as follows: school type, employee number, foundation year of institution, teachers' age, teachers' gender, educational status, total operation time, and operation time in teacher current institution. Besides this demographic research, teacher wage, working environment, and managerial factors are examined to make a remarkable difference in enhancing teachers' performance of work. (Hasbay & Altindag, 2018)

Significant Effects of Supervisory Techniques on Work Performance

The key concern of supervisory techniques practices by the principal is to improve schools' and students' achievements by helping teachers to deliver adequately in their role performance (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2007). In effect, supervisory techniques give teachers opportunities to collaborate, set goals, understand how their students learn and become better teachers through improvement in their work performance. Moreover, the effects of principals' supervisory techniques on the work performance of newly hired teachers were explored using regression analysis, wherein it aims to see how the effects of independent variables on a dependent variable vary between groups in terms of intercept or slope.

In this insight, triangulation combines the different strengths of quantitative and qualitative methods that ensures the sufficient coverage by means of combined survey questionnaire on the supervisory techniques and an online FGD that balance out the significant effect between the principals' supervisory techniques and work performance of newly hired teachers and were validated.

Table 5 reveals the correlation and regression analysis results that principals' supervisory techniques has the mean of 4.58 and pertains to "Very High" in description while the work performance of the newly hired teachers obtained 4.25 as the mean score and has the descriptive interpretation of "High", wherein they were positively correlated hence they are not a significant extent.

Table 5. *Significant Effects of Principals' Supervisory Techniques on Work Performance of Newly Hired Teachers*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>r²</i>	<i>p - value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Principals' Supervisory Techniques	4.58			
			Not Significant	
		0.00	0.867	
Work Performance	4.25			

The table depicts the significant effects of principals' supervisory techniques on the work performance of the newly hired teachers using correlation and regression analysis. It can be deduced from the table that the significant effect of supervisory techniques of the principals on the work performance of newly hired teachers garners a significant p-value of 0.867 which is significantly higher than the cut-off p-value of 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis will be accepted. Therefore, there are no significant effects between the principals' supervisory techniques on the work performance of newly hired teachers.

This result is parallel to the study of Sule (2013) which stated that there was no significant influence of the principal's supervisory techniques on the teachers' work performance. This could be because the technique is largely new to teachers in this part of their field and teachers have not been able to relate to it. Nevertheless, the research statistically concluded that the influence of principal supervision on the performance of teachers is by 21.4% and the remaining 78.6% is influenced by other factors that are not intended variables in this study. It means that the supervision of school principals is one of the factors that affect the performance of teachers in carrying out their duties as teaching staff at school. (Arafat et al., 2018)

In generalizing the claim, it explains that the supervisory technique of principal is not related with the work performance of newly hired teachers mainly because there are lots of aspects which may affect their performance and they are new in the field which are most likely adjusting in the environment and even with their subordinates.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the research paper made the following implications:

The effectiveness and sustainability of the principals' supervisory techniques that applied to the newly hired teachers' work performance device various aspects of supervision and apply the appropriate technique to any of the programs and projected plans. In an effort to made these successful, the principal may be purposeful in thought, motivating, and productivity of other human beings, creative in nature, humanistic in approach, and capable of seeing beyond the level of those whom he or she has to help. Supervisory techniques also aim to improve the incompetent teachers, which provide a guide for professional development. Principals undertake to enlist the co-operation of all teaching personnel in serving their own needs and those of others to prevent teaching difficulties intending to help teachers see more clearly the real ends of education and the specials roles of the should in working towards these goals and lastly, to induct newly hired teachers into this mainstream of the school system and into the teaching profession.

The work performance of the newly hired teachers asserted that they may focus to create a physical, social, and psychological climate or environment favorable to learning and as well as coordinate and integrate all educational efforts and materials which will ensure continuity. The newly hired teachers need to feel supported by colleagues and administration in the professional setting and help them socially navigate the nuances of the cultures of their schools.

The school together with the principal may provide predesigned and structured professional development and other support programs geared toward lessening newly hired teacher attrition to produce more efficient and quality work performance. School-based management can offer support by providing continuous development opportunities such as participation in induction and mentoring processes and professional development activities, and appraisal and feedback like pertinent and constructive performance evaluations can improve the instruction of teachers by highlighting aspects in need of improvement, as well as adequate space and materials. Moreover, they may emphasize to the teachers to know the effectiveness of class management in the new normal education and improve methods of teaching and learning.

The principals may be able to manage the work performance of teachers in school by continuously improving their supervisory techniques specially in instructional supervision and carrying out their responsibilities in managing performance, in this way they may contribute to improving overall teacher performance with a focus on getting better results. Likewise, teachers had to continuously revisit and reflect upon their teaching practices and competencies that need the social support, professional and intellectual stimulation of colleagues and instructional leaders or superiors.

Creating more innovative and motivating supervisory techniques of the principals that may focus on supporting the diverse group of teachers which organize the workflow and ensuring the productivity with constructive technical assistance to each teacher to strengthens professional identity through careful analysis and reflection of personal teaching performance. Additionally, the principals are encouraged to develop a career planning that can be a tool for immediate solution and feedback, also use of differentiated forms of supervision that recognized teacher's potential and address the individual professional development goals as well as the school improvement goals.

In light of the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The contingency theory of leadership used in the study explained that the principals are more contingent and situational leaders that resolve and affect the newly hired teachers in different aspects. As it explained that principals may not affect the newly hired teacher since they are novice in field, supervisory techniques are factor may affect but not as significant.

The conceptual framework of the study also concluded that principals' supervisory techniques are contextualized from the responses from the teachers the that were always observed from their principals were the Workshop and Demonstration Techniques, followed by Monitoring of Work Scheme and Class Observation Technique, and with minor responses were Instructional Supervision and Inspection of Learning Materials and Teaching Resources. In the same structure, majority of the newly hired teachers' work performance attained the descriptive equivalent of Very Satisfactory (VS), wherein Content Knowledge and Pedagogy has the highest weighted mean, followed by the Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners, and Assessment and Reporting. The rest of the indicators gained low scores which are the Curriculum and Planning and Plus Factor.

Moreover, the abovementioned phases were evaluated and process to come up with different products that may produce effectiveness and sustainability of the supervisory techniques of the principals in relation to the teachers' work performance. These said products are the programs that develop both principals and teacher's professional standards, projects that can enhance the ability of the principal to facilitate the teachers in any situation and create a bridge in the blank space of the newly hired teachers in adopting the field of education, and most likely to produce different activities that are suitable for the newly hired teachers which may engage the presence of both principals and teachers which may result for the development of the school and betterment of learning process to the learning even in this changing time of education.

Conclusively, the supervisory techniques of the principals have a descriptive interpretation of "Very High" while the work performance of newly hired teachers obtained a "High" descriptive interpretation based on the correlated and regression analysis used to treat the study.

Furthermore, the null hypothesis of the study which is stating that there is no significant effects of principals' supervisory techniques on work performance of newly hired teacher is accepted.

Several implications drawn from the findings of the study can help for the improvement of the implementation of the principals' supervisory techniques on the work performance of newly hired teachers.

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